

Ulama and Political Thought in Indonesia (A Study of Sufi Thoughts of K.H. Haderanie H.N.)

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Abstract

This study examines the political thoughts of K.H. Haderanie H.N, a prominent Muslims scholar in South Kalimantan, and his track records to the development of neo-sufism in South Kalimantan. A number of literature and his prominent works were collected and analysed using a content analysis technique. The findings showed K.H. Haderanie H.N. introduced the thinking in tasawwuf and politics as an integrative thought as an ulama and politician, he attempted to unite between tarekat ulama and political ulama. There is also a tendency that K.H. Haderanie H.N.put together the aspects of politics and moral values in the political arena in order to form a political pattern guided by the values of the Qur'an and al-Hadith and accompanied by good political morals.

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Introduction

Discussions related to religion and the state become an issue of endless debate. Viewed from the context of history, religion and state are two different natures. Religion is more oriented to the hereafter, while the state is more about the life of the world. Religion is the good news (*basyir*) and warnings (*nazir*), while the state is a force of force. Religion has ulama (Muslim scholars trained in Islam and Islamic law) and missionaries, while the state has bureaucracy, court and army. Religion can influence history through shared consciousness, while the state affects history with decision, power and war. Religion is the power of the inside, while the state is the power of the outside. (Kontowijoyo, 1997: 197)

At present there is a tendency for the dichotomy between religion and state in the political climate. Research in political science shows a very wide and substantial policy gap among leaders, elected people, and mass coalitions (Abramowitz and Saunders 1998; Stonecash, Brewer, and Mariani 2003; Jacobson 2005; McCarty, Poole, and Rosenthal 2006; Theriault 2008; Levendusky 2009; Lee 2009). This gap has spread in a number of policy domains ranging from cultural and lifestyle issues to racial, economic and social welfare issues (Layman and Carsey 2002; Brewer and Stonecash 2007; Layman et al. 2010). This is accompanied by increasing constancy and cruelty in political rhetoric, debates and campaigns, and increasing the inability of both parties to compromise to reach a policy consensus solution (Jamieson and Falk 2000; Sinclair 2006; Brownstein 2007; Levendusky 2013) caused by the position of religion which is seen as contrary to the state, so that Muslims do not play much of their political roles and sometimes are far from the influence of politics and government.

Religion is sometimes seen as contrary to the state. In reality, based on religio-political notions, religion plays a role in explaining variations in religious change in relations between religious and secular actors. Religious changes are important mainly because of their impact on political incentives faced by elites involved in policy debates that impact religious-secular relations (Buckley and Wilcock, 2017). Pancasila, the Indonesian ideology, can be seen in line with Islamic teachings with complementary positions (Beck Irawan, 2016). In addition, Islamic political activities that have not developed strong traditions in government do not play an important role in state institutions and tend to keep their distance from the state. (Effendy, 1998: 53)

Regarding religious and state relations, the ulama has a role as a missionary preacher and at the same time as statesmen and politicians who are involved in the political world. The phenomenon of political ulama is common in Indonesia, especially when it comes to elections where ulama are in great demand by politicians. Politicians often make ulama as a shield and a means to recruit more votes and support for their party. This will gradually drag the ulama leaders into the gates of practical politics, leading to prolonged conflicts among ulama leaders due to differences in interests.

The involvement of ulama leaders in the political arena can also have a negative impact (Umar, 2014: 59) towards the ummah, namely excessive fanaticism. (Sari, 2016: 114-133) This phenomenon is a common thing in the political arena in Indonesia despite many factors behind it. It is very ironic when supporters of the

party make religion the reason when the party is supported by a clerical figure. His followers also concluded that only the party was the most righteous who claimed the truth and ultimately caused excessive fanaticism. So with the jargon of jihad in the way of Allah, there are many assumptions that defending the party is the same as defending religion. (Yazid, 2014)

The facts as mentioned above indeed often occur in political games in Indonesia. But this does not mean that so far the ulama can be dragged away by the interests of the rulers. (Sari, 2016: 126) There are still many ulama who are able to play their role as defenders of religion through the political power they play. It is very reasonable to accept if ulama decides to plunge into the political arena by prioritizing the interests of the state in playing its political role that is objectively upholding religion provided he is not trapped in certain political currents which sometimes have subjective interests that are not in line with religious interests. (Ali, 1999: 33)

Religious and political relations have been widely studied by researchers. Calmers associates ulamas and politics with theological expressions and political activism. Religion is often associated with ethnic problems, and that is what has happened for centuries with Islam and the process of Islamization in Indonesia, especially in South Kalimantan. However, in the past few years, in the area which is now divided into two — Central and South Kalimantan — there is an opinion that religious functions are increasingly weakening as a determinant of ethnic identity. Is that right? To what extent does the process work, and influence the polarization of religions like in the past? This paper explains that, in a changing social context - colored by the dialectic between theological thought and political activism in a long period of time - religion is often no longer bound by certain ethnic types. In turn, it brings religion more as a universal value system. A potential explanation that religion provides a moral authority to the authority of the State (Storm, 2016).

K.H. Haderanie H.N. is one of the ulama figures from Kalimantan who has a great influence in the community. Since 1966, he has begun to actively preach giving guidance to congregations who are scattered in various regions in Banjarmasin, Palangka Raya, Muara Teweh and North Barito. In 1972 he had settled in Surabaya and focused on giving recitation in various regions of Java, including in Jakarta and Yogyakarta. (Rahman, 2007: 23)

The dual role he plays is an interesting thing to examine. When many ulamas are seen as negative (Sari, 2016:126) or even fail when plunging into politics, K.H. Haderanie H,N, he actually got high charismatic from the supporters. (Geertz, 1960: 228-49)

This article attempts to investigate Haderanie's thoughts in politics. In terms of religion, he is a figure of neo-Sufism who has a high charismatic in society. Therefore the article also explores and examines neosufism in his political activities.

A Theory of Ulama and Tasawwuf

In traditional societies ulama still function as a paternalistic and mental-minded awareness so that ulama are not only cultural brokers (Geertz, 1960: 22 8-49) but also as a creator and agent (Horikoshi, 1987: 247) for social change. (Umam, 2015: 4) Ulama are defined as people who are religious and are good in religion or piety to religion. Another term of alim ulama is also called *kiai* (Maulana, tt) as Geertz mentioned, although finally Horikoshi distinguished the term. Ulama are more of an administrative function, but *kiai* are to the cultural level. (Farid, 2007: 238)

The statement proposed by Geertz above was also supported by Deliar Noer who stated that in general the traditional ulama were not active in political matters. Political issues are usually left to customary leaders and ulama are said to have no experience in political matters.

In history, the involvement of ulamas was apparent at the resistance of the Banten peasants (1888) and Cobra Movement (1871) in Sumatera and Kalimantan (1821-1838). Therefore, Dhofier and Horikoshi denied that the role of the *kiai* was very large, especially in politics in the party in the General Election. (Umar, 2014: 59)

Martin van Bruisnessen also emphasized that the role of ulama is very strategic not only in deciding religious issues but also in socio-political problems. He gave an example of Qadhi who was also a Sufism expert in the sultanate of Banten who played a large role which did not exist in Java at that time.

Ali Maschan Moesa mentions the typology of ulama or *kiai* into four types: (1) pesantren ulama, namely *kiai* who focus their attention on increasing community resources through education or pesantren, (2) tarekat ulama, namely *kiai* who study in the world of mysticism and build intelligence of the public, (3) political ulama, namely *kiai* who develop organizations such as NU and Muhammadiyah involved in the world of politics and government, (4) stage ulama, namely *kiai* who actively give religious lectures in various places. (Moesa, 2007: 65-66) In the context of the history of typology, scholars can be categorized into four typologies, namely: first is a group of scholars who concurrently as the ruler of the central government. The second type is the class of scholars who are still of noble blood. The third type is the ulama group as a tool of the old royal bureaucracy as a tool of the royal / traditional bureaucracy. The fourth type is a group of rural scholars who live in villages and there is no pathway with bureaucracy. The ulama of this village work independently according to their own willingness to develop Islam in their area. (see: Shokheh, 2011)

In politics, the issue of religious and state relations is one of the main debates in the world political climate, especially among Muslims. At least there are two main conflicting patterns, namely secularistic and integrative patterns, which are then followed by patterns that mediate between the two, namely symbiotic patterns.

- a. Secularistic pattern, introduced by Jacob Holyoake around 1846 in England. There are three main reasons underlying: orientation to the present world, Western science and liberalism. Karl Marx is different from Jacob who opposes religion indirectly, so Marx actually displays a more extreme style, where he considers religion to be something that is not real and a human ignorance of the reality of life.
- b. Integrative pattern, which is played by fundamental groups, namely the movement pushing towards religion. This ideology is contrary to secularism.
- c. Symbiotic patterns played by moderate groups. Modernist flows, such as Natsir, say creating a mutual relationship between religion and state. The state can be built on a clear religious basis.

In the context of Sufism and politics, the type of a cleric or kiai has three typologies in dealing with power, namely struggle within, struggle from without and cooperative conditionally. Struggle from within groups engage in active interaction with the dominant power of the government. The group struggle from without makes distance from the dominant group, while cooperatively conditionally communicates as limited as the government to create the benefits of the development of Sufism. (Sahri, 2011: 124-39)

B. Method

This study attempts to analyze political thoughts of KH. Haderanie HN using the sociological framework of knowledge, which states that “sociology of knowledge is concerned with the relationship between human thought and the social context within which it arises) (Burger and Luckman, 1966; Kuntowijoyo, 2003; 200).

This study uses content analysis carried out descriptively based on the work of books written by Haderanie, namely *Permata yang Indah* (1987), *Ilmu Ketuhanan (Ma'rifat, Musyahadah, Mukasyafah, dan Mahabbah)* (1991), *Asma al Husna: Sumber Ajaran Tauhid/Tasawwuf* (1992), *Maut dan Dialog Suci* (1993), and *Hikam Melayu* (1999). Works written by Haderanie were selected purposively to examine his thoughts related to politics. Data were also gathered from mass media documentation about his political activities, such as 30 articles from *Kalteng Post* in 1987-2001. Haderanie is known as a figure of neo-Sufism but, on the other hand, he is also a political figure. Data from website or agency that contains or publishes his or her thoughts were also analyzed.

This research emphasizes explorative studies by exploring deeply the thoughts of KH. Haderanie HN with descriptive narrative techniques. This method focuses on understanding data by means of classification, categorization and taxonomy. After that the researcher constructs it into a unified whole that ends in political thinking of KH. Haderanie HN.

C. Findings and Discussion

1. Findings

a. A Profile of KH. Haderanie H.N.

KH. Haderanie bin H. Nawawi bin H. Abdul Hamid was born to the Malay family of Banjar Bakumpai on August 16, 1933 in Puruk Cahu, a religious court in Barito Regency, Kalimantan Province before Kalimantan was divided into five provinces. He was the tenth son of H. Nawawi bin H. Abdul Hamid from the country with Masudah bint H. Adam from Bakumpai. He comes from a strong elite religious family with Islamic nuances to the full extent of his Islamic teaching in his family, from learning "*ngaji*" (reading the Koran) to learning the basic knowledge of other Islamic religions (Rahman, 2004: 6).

Since he was in Madrasah Ibtida'iyah - junior high school level-, he aspired to become a muballigh. The small emperor was very diligent to learn the religion of his mother, then to the mother-in-law abducted by the fifth descendant of Sheikh Muhammad Arsyad al-Banjārī. While sitting at the First Islamic Middle School, he also followed the Light Education Muballigh led by KH. Asnawi Hadisiswoyo (who was then Head of Religious Affairs Office in Kalimantan in 1950). He was recommended by Lord Guru Haji Suriansyah to attend Kulliyah Muballighin education in Semarang, Central Java. Furthermore, he studied, among others, to KH. Zainal Ilmi (Martapura), KH Hanafi Gobet (Banjarmasin), and KH. Abdussamad (Alabio). Furthermore, he continued his education at Madrasah Muballighin and Kulliyah Muballighin in Semarang, with Prof. KH. Saifudin Zuchri. He is a companion with KH. Musta'in Ramli and KH. Najib Wahab Hasbullah (Rois Awwal Syuriyah NU center). He is an adherent of the Syaziliyah Shaikh (Shaykh Abū Hasan al-Syāzili) following the remarks of Shaikh Abū Alawī Abd al-Hāmid Alawī al-Kaff (Mecca) which was later revealed to his nine students in Palangkaraya. In 1955, Haderanie and Usman Rafiq, Mawardi Yasin, Tarmizi, and Gusti Muhammad Yusuf built the Nahdlatul Ulama (NU) organization in Muara Teweh, Barito. He also served as the administrator of the Central Kalimantan NU Regional Leadership Council (DPW) since its inception until 2005 and also a member of the NU Executive Board (PB) from 1999-2004. When he was 23 years old, he served as chairman of the Barito council, Wk. The Chairperson of the Barito Council, before the division of Borneo into 4 Provinces -

(U.U 27/59). In 1967 he was appointed as a member of the Daily Government Body in Central Kalimantan, with the task of assisting the Governor, until the end of his term in 1972. He married Mastian Ruslin bint Asran bin Ahmad, who was later blessed with nine children: Ashary, Astuti Rahmi, Madurasmi, Murniwati, Asrarul Haq, Asmarani, Asyraful Auliya, Asyiah Arrani (passed away), and Kumala Sari (Vieya, 2013).

As a teacher, KH.Haderanie HN has taught English and book at SMEP State and State Senior High School in Muara Teweh. In addition, he has also been a lecturer at the Faculty of Tarbiyah of the State Islamic Religious Institute (IAIN) Antasari Branch of Palangkaraya with Tauhid and Tasawwuf courses. As a preacher, he led special studies of Tauhid and Tasawwuf in Banjarmasin (1966-1967), Palangkaraya, Muara Teweh to remote areas of North Barito, especially in Puruk Cahu (now Murung Raya) and Surabaya. In politics, in 1955 was active in NU Political Party. In 1972 he moved to Surabaya and stayed there until he taught Tauhid and Tasawwuf and wrote and published several books, among others: (1) Ma'rifat, Musyahadah, Mukasyafah, and Mahabbah (4M); (2) Asmaul Husna Sumber Ilmu Tauhid / Tasawwuf; (3) Beautiful Gems (translator and lecturer on al-Durr al-Nafis by Nafis al-Banjārī; and (4) Death and Sacred Dialogue (translated from Mukhtashar al-Taḥkīr karya al-Qurṭubī).

In his daily life, Haderanie is more focused on the teaching of Sufism, ranging from the scope of his family in Muara Teweh to outside the area even outside the island of Borneo. Even though he was active in politics, he never destroyed the charismatic mysticism of Sufism. In fact, he was able to unite the two elements that appeared to be contradictory so that a new term emerged, political mysticism which played a political role based on Sufism values.

KH.Haderanie HN passed away on Sunday, December 28, 2008 at 6:35 p.m. or at 5:35 p.m. at the Ulin Hospital in Banjarmasin. His funeral was led by Deputy Chairperson of DPD Irman Gusman at the funeral home Jl Kinibalu No 62 Bukit Hindu, Palangkaraya, Monday (29/12), and was buried in the Muslim Cemetery Complex Jl. Tjilik Riwt Km 2.5 Palangkaraya, Central Kalimantan (Kabar Indonesia, 30 December 2008).

b. Religious Activities

KH.Haderanie H.N. can be classified as one of the leading contemporary Sufi figures in Central Kalimantan who emerged with his Sufism teachings. His existence represents the dynamics of new Sufism (neo-Sufism) thinking in the modern era. He directs the teachings of Islamic spirituality in an effort to purify the elements and practices that deviate from pure Islam which thrives in the Muslim community of Central Kalimantan. (Rahman, 2004: 1). In fact, Sufism has influenced Muslim religious life in Kalimantan, since the 18th century until now. The tendency to combine Sufism ethics al-Ghazālī and metaphysical Sufism Ibn'Arabī is a respect for Sufi figures in the ritual of reading manakib, and the emergence of splinter tasawwuf groups. All of this can be found throughout Islamic history in this area (Mujiburrahman, 2013: 153).

Genealogically thinking, KH.Haderanie HN is a consistent ulama to restore Sufism on the right track as the two Banjar ulamas have done, namely Shaykh Muhammad Arsyad al-Banjārī and Shaykh Muhammad Nafis al-Banjārī, and at the same time reviving Sufism in the modern era. The main reason KH. Haderanie HN revives Sufism is the fact that reasoning alone will not be able to achieve the 'meaning and meaning of nature' of Allah. Of course Sufism does not mean to discuss the nature of the form of God, because something that is impossible to talk about is sought because there is certainty 'laisa kamiṣlihi syai'un' (nothing like Him) (Haderanie, tthb: 45). Another reason is KH Haderanie HN's efforts to purge Sufism from negativism towards activism, and local elements that are contrary to true Sufism. In this regard, this study will analyze the Sufism thoughts of KH. Haderanie HN with academic questions: how is the construct of neo-Sufism thinking from KH.Haderanie HN and its relevance to modern life?

Many religious knowledge is obtained by KH. Haderanie H.N. of his formal education. However, he still took time to study sit (for classical religious education in Banjar language) and asked for a diploma degree with ulamas in the area. Some ulamas who have been their teachers are: KH. Habran from the Tumbukan Banyu, KH. Ali Negara, KH. Hanafi Gobet, Banjarmasin, and KH. Abdussomad, Alabio. From his non-formal education he gained a lot of understanding of religious science, especially tasawwuf. While in the science of tarekat KH.Haderanie joined Shaikh Abul Hasan al-Syadzily and took the Talqin Zikir Degree from Shaykh Abu 'Alawi' Abd al-Hamid 'Alawi al-Kaf during his pilgrimage in 2001.

Since being appointed as a member of the Daily Government Agency in 1967, he actively spread Sufism in Palangka Raya, and in 1972 he moved to Surabaya and focused on spreading Sufism in Surabaya and Jakarta, sometimes coming to Banjarmasin, Palangka Raya and Muara Teweh.

In 1992 KH.Haderanie was given the mandate as chairman of the Indonesian Ulama Board (MUI), Central Kalimantan. In the Regional Conference at the end of his second term, namely the 2003 MUI Regional Secretary of Central Kalimantan, he was severely criticized through newspapers, one of which was to prevent him from participating again in the election for the next MUI Chair.*However, based on the results of the Regional Musda which was held for two days and the nine-person formation team, KH.Haderanie H.N. was

**Arsip Menyambut Musda IV MUI Kalteng*, Kamis 28 Juli 2003.

finally set as General Chairperson of the MUI in Central Kalimantan in 2003-2008. Thus, KH.Haderanie H.N. again trusted to in three consecutive periods.[†]

Some thoughts of neosufism of KH Haderanie HN include:

Renewal of Sufism (neo-Sufism) carried out by KH. Haderanie H.N. both directly and indirectly is the continuity and sustainability of the renewal movement in Kalimantan in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries through what was called by Azyumardi Azra (1994) with 'the ulama network of Middle Eastern ulamas and the archipelago'. The most prominent feature of the reform movement at that moment was the mutual approach (reapprochement) when the shari'a-oriented ulama (more specifically, the fuqahā) and the Sufis reach their peak. The longstanding conflict between the two groups of Muslim ulamas seems to have diminished a lot; mutual attitudes or reconciliation between them - which were taught persistently by ulamas such as al-Qusyairī and al-Ghazālī several centuries earlier - were carried out by many ulamas. Most of them were ahl al-syārī'ah (fuqahā ') and ahl al-ḥaqīqah (Sufi) all at once. The mutual attitude of the approach between Shari'a and Sufism (Sufism) and the entry of the ulama into the tarekat resulted in the emergence of 'neo-Sufism' (Azra, 1994: 109).

The focus of neo-Sufism is the socio-moral reconstruction of the Muslim community. This is different from the previous Sufism, which primarily emphasizes the individual and not the community (Rahman, 1970: 637). Thus, the overall character of neo-Sufism is puritan and activist (Rahman, 1979: 194). His practitioners did not resign from the life of the world, but instead made the inner detachment to achieve more spiritual realization (Azra, 2002: 194). Neo-sufism tends to reinforce positive attitude to the world (Madjid, 1995: 94). The neo-Sufi also acknowledged, to some extent, the truth of intellectual Sufism claims: they accept the kasyf (experience of divine truth) the Sufi or intuitive inspiration but reject their claim as incorrect (ma'sūm), emphasizing that reliability kasyf is comparable to the moral cleanliness of the heart, which actually has infinite levels (Madjid, 1995: 94).

For the context of Kalimantan, especially South Kalimantan, there are two important ulamas who brought the renewal movement of Sufism, namely Shaykh Muhammad Arsyad al-Banjārī (1122-1127/1710-1812) and Shaykh Muhammad Nafīs al-Banjārī (lahir 1148/1735) (Azra, 1994: 251-257). The trace of the reform of these two ulamas can be found in the mind and practice of tasawwuf in South Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan today. The strong evidence of continuity and sustainability of the renewal movement against KH.Haderanie HN is seen from translation and lecturing on al-Durr al-Nafīs by Nafīs al-Banjārī. In his al-Durr al-Nafīs, Nafīs al-Banjārī emphasized the absolute transcendence and the oneness of God, rejecting the opinion of Jabariyah that defended the fatalistic determinism in contravention of the free will (Qadariyah). According to the opinion of Nafīs al-Banjārī, Muslims must strive to achieve a better life by doing good deeds and avoiding evil (Nafīs al-Banjārī, th: 3). Thus, Nafīs al-Banjārī is clearly a supporter of activism, one of the basic features of neosufism. According to Azyumardi Azra (1994: 257) with strong pressure on Muslim activism, it is not surprising that al-Durr al-Nafīs was banned by the Dutch, because it was feared that it would encourage Muslims to launch jihad. The aim of the renewal of other tasawwuf is also aimed at rectifying excessive respect for the guardians of Allah, and the traditions or thoughts claimed as manifestations of Sufism, among others, the concept of the Science of Alif which is considered part of Sufism. It is believed that humans in the afterlife will manifest in various circumstances. In order for a tangible human body as it is in the world, Alif Science is practiced. This science is practiced in every prayer. If someone does not remember it, then he will lose a limb in the hereafter.

"Alif is between my foreheads on my body. Bā is my right forehead. Tā is my left forehead. Sā is my forehead. Jīm is my head and the door of the Ka'bah on my body. Hā is my right shoulder. Khā is my left shoulder. Dāl is my right leg. Zāl is my left foot. Rā is my right rib. Zai is my left rib. Sīn is my right chest. Syīn is my left chest. Šād is my right ear. Dād is my left ear. Tā is my right eye. Zā is my left eye. 'Ain is my right hand. Ghīn is my left hand. Fā is my right waist. Qāf is my left waist. Kāf is my right back. Lām is my left back. Mīm is my face. Nūn is my brain. Wawu is my navel, batu depends on my body. Hā is my heart. Ka'bah is in my body. Lām alif my shulbi bone, 'arsyis the chair on my body. Hamzah is my heart. Yā is my soul, the secret of God is in my body"(Hermansyah, 2010: 197-198).

It may be the fallacy of Sufism's understanding as above due to the method of teaching Sufism which is considered as a special science, which is very confidential, so that not just anyone learns it. KH.Haderanie regretted that Sufism was considered a secret; study of Sufism-Godness must have understood very well in matters of the Shari'a, the depth of his jurisprudence, must know all the laws in detail (tafšīlī). In addition, some say: "Let us not give this secret knowledge to anyone other than that." (Haderanie, thb: 187). As a result, according to Haderanie, many Sufi studies are being hidden and taught by non-members. It is more reminiscent:

"Humans want to seek inner satisfaction by seeking knowledge in that direction [tasawwuf—pen], however, given the various conditions and conditions that it is difficult to implement at the end, they retreat regularly or inclinate the inclination to fill the mind in practical ways, which otherwise generate reverse results

[†]Haderani 3 Kali Pimpin MUI, Kalteng Post, Selasa 16 September 2003.

that are not in accordance with the true teachings. However, they feel the inner fill of their wishes. We should not be surprised that people who are in a deserted desert area and do not find anything for thirst releases, at the moment-then, dirty water will somehow be taken. As mentioned by Rasulullah 'Kāda al-faqrū yurist al-kufra' (almost the needy suffer from infidelity).'

My teachers and myself disgree that to study this must always be complete with other sciences. The definition that is said to be 'expert' is people who have intelligence to explore inner problems. Of course they must understand which are good and which are bad, even though they are *ijmālī* (global). As a Muslim, they certainly understand and say the words of the creed, prayer, fasting and so on that they carry out" (Haderanie, tt: 188).

Although there is an obligation to teach Sufism openly, KH.Haderanie acknowledges that there are many expressions and formulas and signals in this science that must be understood. Thus, Haderanie emphasized the importance of a teacher to help reveal the meaning of the *tasawwuf's* "expressions, formulas and cues". Without the teacher, there are many possibilities for misunderstanding which results in misleading results. Therefore, once again, Haderanie emphasized:

"The teacher is not someone who can certainly take his students to reach God. Not at all. Teachers are just showing the way, giving understanding. But all of that is entirely dependent on God's own will. Especially when it comes to the essential understanding of *makrifat* is 'God Himself who introduced Himself'. (Haderanie, tt: 178).

Relationships with a teacher are considered an absolute condition for spiritual success. Without the presence of a teacher, someone is feared to fall into error. This is what is meant by the famous Sufi statement: "Whoever does not have a *shaykh*, a devil who will become his *shaykh*." A true teacher, of course, is one who has made it that way, who knows his likeness, pitfalls and the dangers, so he can guide others. When a student has been accepted by the teacher, he must surrender himself completely to the teacher and seem to be "the body in the hands of the person who bathes it." The purpose of this surrender is to conquer the ego, experience psychic death, which marks true birth into the spiritual life (Michon, 2002: 367). A well-known example of the benefits of being submissive to a teacher, is written by Jalal al-Din Rumi, a renowned spiritual teacher and founder of the Maulawi Order. He left his position as professor of religious sciences in Konya to follow the spiritual teachings of the mystic figure Shams al-Din Tabrizī. Through this teacher and surrender to him, Rūmī reached the highest peak in Divine Love and contemplative vision (Michon, 2002: 368; Kartanegara, 1986: 36-45).

To learn more about the functions of spiritual teachers, Seyyed Hossein Nasr, has formulated the following:

"The role of the spiritual teacher — *shaykh*, *murshid*, or *pīr*, as he knows Arabic, Persian, and other Muslim languages — is to allow the student to undergo the process of rebirth and spiritual change. Because he is connected through a series of continuous genealogies to the Prophet and with the function of initiation (*wilāyah*) inherent in the prophetic message itself, Sufi teachers are able to liberate humans from the narrow boundaries of the material world to enter the luminous space of the spiritual life. Close to the perfect teacher means regaining ecstasy and the joy of spring life. Separating from the teacher is tantamount to feeling suffering and aging. Entering a Sufi order and accepting a position as a student from a true teacher means entering into an eternal bond, which can survive even from death" (Nasr, 1972: 57-59).

Furthermore Nasr said: "Humans can find their own springs of life. He can try to find the principles of spiritual regeneration through his own efforts. However, this effort will be in vain and will not be useful unless the teacher is present with the students to be taught. Without a philosopher's stone, there could be no alchemical change. Only the power of the *shaykh* can free man from himself from his physical soul so that it enables him to draw closer to the realm of Nature and reenter it into the ocean Universal existence of death" (Nasr, 1972: 58).

Straightening the Concept of *Ma'rifah Allāh* (Knowing Allah), since the third century Hijri or IX century AD Sufism began to get its clear form as an Islamic mystic (Baisūnī, 1969: 5-25; Karamustafa, 2007). At that time the Sufis had talked about *makrifat*. What is meant by *makrifat* is to know the Lord directly, with the inner sight or the heart which has received His light, and immersed in His Absolute Unity in such a way so what was seen by the Sufi at that time only He (Allah) (Nasution, 1985: 51-67; Isa, 2001: 45).

KH.Haderanie HN wrote a special book that talks about four important concepts in Sufism: *makrifat*, *musyāhadah*, *mukāsāyah*, and *maḥabbah* (4M). What's interesting about this book is when the author begins his discussion of the concept of somewhat "odd" *makrifat* in his hometown, which is different from the concept of Sufism above. He said that his experience in studying with his teacher has taught him the nature of *makrifat*.

"Uluh ji jida maku mangatawani kungaie, sama beh dengan lanjung buang. Itah tuh harus mangatawani, narai asal kunge, narai aran asli kungetuh, kueh andakaie petak asal Nabi Adam si huang kunge, dan narai aran petak jite. Alam semesta tuh ada si huang kunge ada matan andau huang kunge, matan andau ji bagerek dan ji jida bagerek, ada angin, ada danum, sungai, petak, wasi, wasi kuning, naraka, sorga uras ada si huang kunge itah kabuat. Yaweh ji jida katawan sorga huang kunge dan aran sorga te, ela harap ie mengkeme ji aran sorga. Jibril, Mikail, Izrail, Israfil ataupun Abu Bakar, Umar, Usman, Ali, samandeah-e ada si huang

kunge dan ada arai-e masing-masing. Yaweh ji handak jagao, harus katawan narai aran asli Izrail pencabut nyawa, dan aran Saidina Ali ji asli-e. Harus katawan si kueh andakai-e si kungan itah. Ka'bah ada si huang kunge, yaweh katawan andakai-e dan aran asli-e, biar jida usah mandai Haji kan Makah, sama beh dengan mandai haji..."

"People who do not want to know themselves, are just like an empty sack. We need to know where we are from and what our real name is. Where is the place of Adam's inner existence and what the name of the land is. The universe is all inside, there is the sun inside, the wind, the water, the river, the ground, the iron, the yellow iron, the hell, the heaven, all within us. Who does not know the heaven in himself and the name of heaven, do not expect him to feel heaven. Jibril, Mikail, Izrail, Israfil or Abu Bakr, Umar, Usman, Ali, are all inside and there are also their real names. Who wants to be good, should know what Izrail's and Saidina Ali's real name is, and should know where it is located. Ka'bah is also inside of us. Who knows the location of the Ka'bah and the original name, though not going to Mecca, is worth the pilgrimage..." (Haderanie, ttha: 14-15). Studying the above knowledge takes three consecutive nights. The condition is to know the names the teacher intended and to know where they are in the body (Rahman, 2004: 12). This teacher's teachings after being understood very seriously did not have anything to do with the science of makrifat or tasawwuf knowledge as in Islam. In fact, there are certain parts that lead to error. For example, understanding the Ka'bah in itself allows one, even though it has the ability to follow Islam, to abandon the final pillar of Islam, that is to perform the pilgrimage to the Holy Land (Haderanie, ttha: 16). In fact, Sufism cannot be separated from the Shari'a. KH.Haderanie HN emphasized: "If there is a teaching that says that the teaching is a genuine and true teaching of tasawwuf but abandoning the law of syarak, then it is clear that the teaching is misguided" (Haderanie, tt: 43); "if you are convinced and fallen by the Islamic (or non-religious) taklifs, then you fall into a sect called the zindik infidels" (Haderanie, tt: 27). According to KH.Haderanie, Sufism teachings are teachings of inner purity and concerning the esoteric aspects of Islam which merely directs its seeker to be able to enter ḥaḍrat al-qudsiyah (hadrat purity) with perfect ma'rifah (recognition) in order to musyāhadah (witness) and mukāsyafah (inner open) with the pouring of maḥabbah (love) from Him (Haderanie, tt: 13). Makrifat or gnosticakan can be obtained as long as the teachings adhered to are true teachings that have a great influence on one's self-formation and can decorate themselves with praiseworthy traits (maḥmūdah) as well as being able to avoid being reprehensible (maẓmūmah) (Haderanie, tt: 14). Thus, recognizing this self will lead people to continuously trace their authenticity which ends up in only displaying commendable character. Moral which is the light of God will enter his heart. So, no human being is able to know Him in an intrinsic sense except with His will (Haderanie, tthb: 181). He himself will introduce (Haderanie, tt: 118).

c. Political Record

In 1956 Haderanie was elected as a member of the DPRD in the election of Barito at the age of 23 years. Serving as chairman of the DPRD was a brilliant initial achievement for KH. Haderanie H.N. While serving as chairman of the DPRD, there were six political parties: three Islamic political parties, namely Nahdatul Ulama, Masyumi and PPTI, and three other national parties, namely the Indonesian National Party (PNI), the Indonesian Communist Party (PKI) and the Indonesian People's Party (PRN).

In 1967 KH.Haderanie H.N. appointed as Governor in the Central Kalimantan Provincial Government (BPH) member. He has served as a member of the MPR RI Central Kalimantan regional delegation from 1999 to 2004. For his brilliant efforts in providing outstanding service and contributions to the people and government of Central Kalimantan, he was given an honorary title as Doctor Honoris Causa (Dr. HC) by the Regents of Northern California Global University Team in Jakarta on May 28, 1992.

d. Intellectual Works

As a highly charismatic ulama, KH.Haderanie H.N. is not only known as a Sufism teacher and a political figure, but also is known through his works that have been published and spread to various regions throughout Kalimantan and outside Kalimantan, such as:

- a. *Permata yang Indah (Ad Dur an-Nafis)*, CV. Amin Surabaya, 1987.
- b. *Ilmu Ketuhanan, Ma'rifat, Musyadah, Mukasyafah, dan Mahabbah (4M)* CV. Amin Surabaya, 1991.
- c. *Asma al Husna, Sumber Ajaran tauhid/Tasawwuf* PT. Bina Ilmu Surabaya, 1992.
- d. *Maut dan Dialog Suci*, CV. Amin Surabaya 1993.
- e. *Hikam Melayu*, CV. Amin Surabaya, 1999.

In addition to the works of tasawwuf, he also wrote about the issue of jurisprudence, namely *Menyingkap Tabir dalam Ibadah Haji* [the disclosure of Tabir in Hajj], published by CV Amin Surabaya in 1994. Then about the family problem, namely *Keluarga Sejahtera dalam Bahasa Agama* [the prosperous family in Religious Language], published by CV. Amin Surabaya.

2. Discussion (Political Thoughts of KH. Haderanie H.N.)

Politics and government according to KH.Haderanie is an important element in determining the future of the people. This is in line with the role of ulama as a guide to the Ummah. With the support of the ulama, the government will be able to carry out the government process properly. In addition, ulama can uphold their functions more effectively with government support.

An article about KH.Haderanie stated that the government is an important element in the efforts to progress Muslims. Therefore, the government needs to be supported by the role of ulamas. There are at least three programs that can be applied by ulama, namely concern for the ukhuwah Islamiyah people with feelings of love, and increasing human resources (HR) in addition to other basic efforts namely amar ma'ruf nahi munkar. (Haderani: 30)

KH.Haderanie also hopes that Muslims, especially the younger generation, can participate in the government. This is done in order to increase human resources so that they are not left behind and discriminated against by other parties.

According to several sources including Said Fawzy and Samsuri Yusuf, KH.Haderanie stated that if someone said that politics was not good and tended to do things that were less positive and did not contain Islamic values, then that was not true. That is what is held by KH. Haderanie that Islam must take part in politics and politics is not always dirty.

According to Azyumardi Azra, the relationship between religion and the ruler is not always seen as negative because power can be a vehicle for the development of Islam through education. For example, ulamas can develop Islamic educational institutions such as madrasa and so on. (Azra, 2002 :78-81)

Material shortcomings and political powerlessness will make it difficult to uphold worship and syiar. Welfare and religiosity are contained in the concept of izzul Islam wa almuslimin which can be realized in many ways including obtaining high positions in the fields of politics, economics and society.(Fealy, 2009: 84-5)

Some political thoughts in the form of special concepts of KH.Haderanie H.N. include:

a. Balance of the World And Hereafter

The reality of human life, according to KH.Haderanie, always wants the success of the world and the hereafter even though in reality it is difficult to be right in the middle position and get both. Thus, the solution offered is to determine the percentage of each of the needs of the world and the hereafter according to its portion. He mentions the following:

Humans have many interests and necessities of life. In the global sense, there are two main interests and necessities of life, namely the interests of the world and the interests of the hereafter. For this reason, humans need to succeed as much as possible and enjoy their interests. To realize these two kinds of interests, humans do have limitations. Therefore, the choice factor must exist according to its limitations. With the determination of choice, for example a percentage for the interests of the world for the remainder of the interests of the hereafter, the level of effort of achievement is measured generally against the real thing. (Kafie, 1983: 102)

b. Nationalism

Set against Western thought, Muslims see the world of Islam which is very backward from a social, economic, cultural and religious standpoint. Regarding nationalism issues, KH.Haderanie H.N. not in line with people who think that expressive culture has left this nation behind. According to him, the influence of colonialism made this nation colonized for centuries. He mentions the following:

One expert pointed out that we are left behind in the nation's development because it is too strong with the expressive culture of ancestral heritage values which are dominated by the values of religion, art and power, values that emphasize inner aspects, imagination and feelings (Jawa Pos, 1990).

On the contrary, KH.Haderanie asserted that expressive culture had contributed to the spirit of struggle until the Indonesian people succeeded in ousting the invaders and gaining independence. In fact, according to him religious values have become the most important principle and philosophy for the Indonesian people. He mentions the following:

“Religion and the feeling of mysticism have served to build the spirit of idealism to drive out colonialism from this beloved country. Last but not least religion has contributed to expelling communism and teachings from Indonesia. Communism is always oriented to science and economics, which totally ignores religious values, values of inner feelings. Pancasila as the only principle and philosophy of the Indonesian Nation has the Supreme Belief and places religion in a high and noble position, upholds the values of feeling and heart”. (Interview)

Based on the explanation above, KH.Haderanie, H.N. attempts to remind the history of the Indonesian nation's struggle which was characterized by a spirit of religion. The spirit of political jurisprudence and morality of Sufism succeeded in giving its own color to the spirit of the Indonesian people to fight for the independence of the Indonesian people. Even, the spirit of religion has become the philosophy and ideology of the nation which is conceptualized in the first principle of Pancasila.

c. Multicultural Politics

In terms of finding a leader (governor and deputy for example), there are three criteria that must be considered, one of which is religion. A leader should be Muslim. However, it does not mean that Islam must

seize everything, but share, for example Isla with Non Muslim. In this way, unity in society can be achieved and that is the symbol and nature of unity (especially in the land of Tambun Bungai) (Kalteng Post, 2005)

On another occasion KH.Haderanie H.N. also mentioned three criteria for candidates who were eligible to be elected in the Central Kalimantan provincial election in 2005-2010. However, he did not mention Islam as one of them, but it must be young people. On that occasion, he also stated that all candidates had their respective strengths and good potential to lead Central Kalimantan. (Kalteng Post, 2005)

The statement does not mean aborting the main conditions of a leader who must come from Islam. The statement shows more a sense of humanity and awareness of the condition of the people of Central Kalimantan who have diverse religious and cultural backgrounds.

E. Conclusion

Haderanie's thinking in tasawwuf and politics is an integrative thought and is included in the conditional cooperative typology in tasawwuf that combines syari'at with makrifat. In relation to the power, Haderanie was one who developed the organization and plunged into a political party: the unity between tarekat ulama and political ulamas.

Based on the results of a study of Haderanie political thought, researchers found a tendency that Haderanie combined the political and moral aspects of Islamic jurisprudence in the political play he played, so that his political pattern was always guided by the values of the Qur'an and al-Hadith and accompanied by good political morals. This is reflected in his thinking about the balance of life of the world and the hereafter, including the balance of religion and state, the values of nationalism and the defense of the state, multicultural politics or tolerance in politics.

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